

MEDICAL SCIENCES

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF TAKING IMPRESSIONS TOGETHER WITH THE PROSTHESIS FOR ITS REPAIR

Gurskaya N.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Rustamov E.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Ashrafov D.

Department of Orthopedic Dentistry, Assistant

Abstract

The prevalence of dental defects among the population is 70%, according to WHO [1, 6]. Such a high percentage is associated with several factors, such as the low level of dental care in rural areas, late visits to the dentist in cities, as well as iatrogenic errors in the treatment of caries and its complications [2, 5].

Keywords: plate dentures, repair of dentures, self-hardening plastic.

We conducted a study of the need of patients for treatment with partial removable laminar dentures depending on the age of visits to the dental clinic.

All patients were divided into two groups taking into account the WHO age classification: from 35 to 44 years (80 people) and from 45 to 60 years (72). Therefore, comparing the high prevalence of dentition defects and the need for prosthetics with partial removable plate dentures, it is also necessary to pay attention to the repair of these dentures with the installation of artificial teeth, and in particular to improving the quality of the impressions obtained for repairs [7-9]. Obtaining alginate impressions when repairing partial removable laminar dentures with standard spoons allows for displacement of the denture base, which leads to its loose fit to the prosthetic bed during this manipulation. As a result, there is a discrepancy between the relief of the prosthetic bed and the inner surface of the prosthesis, and this in turn leads to the need for correction of the prosthesis after repair and longer adaptation of the patient [3, 4].

The purpose of the study is to improve the quality of repair of partial removable laminar dentures by improving the technique of obtaining an impression.

Material and methods.

Standard metal spoon, base wax, self-hardening plastic. On a standard metal tray, the projection of the location of the stops, which should be located in all functional groups according to the base of the prosthesis and artificial teeth, is first marked with a chemical pencil or marker. Next, stops for the width of the spoon, 3-4 mm high, are made from wax or self-hardening plastic. Then the prosthesis is inserted into the oral cavity, the impression mass is prepared, and with this spoon an impression is obtained along with the design of a partial removable laminar denture [3]. Over the course of 1 year, we repaired removable laminar dentures in 30 patients (17 women, 13 men) aged 35 to 60 years. Of these, 14 patients (8 women, 6 men) were repaired using the standard method, and 16 patients (9 women, 7 men) were repaired using the method proposed by us.

Results. To assess the accuracy of the fit of the prosthesis base to the prosthetic bed, a section of the

laminar dentures was carried out after receiving impressions using the standard method and the method proposed by us. The accuracy of the fit could be judged by the thickness of the corrective mass applied to the inner surface of the prosthesis base before taking impressions using both methods. When taking an impression using the standard method, the thickness of the layer of corrective mass was 2.56 ± 1.14 mm, and using the method we proposed, it was within 0.64 ± 0.16 mm, which is not significant. After repairing the prosthesis using the standard method, the patient required correction of the prosthesis in subsequent visits, up to three visits, and the method we developed made it possible to eliminate multiple corrections and long-term adaptation of the patient to a partial removable laminar denture after its repair.

Conclusion. Thus, taking impressions when repairing laminar dentures using the method proposed by us increases the accuracy of the fit of the prosthesis base to the prosthetic bed and thereby improves the quality of repair of the prosthesis, which is reflected in the patient's faster adaptation to the prosthesis and in less correction after repair. This, in turn, improves the ergonomics of the doctor's work, which is reflected in less time spent on each patient.

References

1. Zhil'cova E.S., Vorob'eva M.V., Shherbakova T.A. Preimushhestva primeneniya irrigatora u lic, pol'zujushhihsja zubnymi protezami. V sb.: *Jeffektivnaja klinicheskaja praktika: problemy i vozmozhnosti sovremennogo vracha. Sbornik materialov mezhdunarodnoj nauchno-prakticheskoj konferencii. Pod red. Gorshunovoj N.K.* 2017;217-225.
2. Konnov V.V., Pichugina E.N., Popko E.S., Arushanjan A.R., Pylaev Je.V. Myshechno-sustavnaja disfunkcija i ee vzaimosvjaz' s okkluzionnymi narushenijami. *Sovremennye problemy nauki i obrazovanija.* 2015;6-0:131.
3. Arushanjan A.R., Konnov V.V., Bizjaev A.A., Domenjuk D.A., Pylaev Je.V., Konnov S.V. Obektivnye metody ocenki kachestva ranee izgotovlennyh nesemnyh konstrukcij zubnyh protezov. *Zhurnal*

nauchnyh statej Zdorov'e i obrazovanie v XXI veke. 2017;19:10:29-31.

4. Olenko A.A., Matycina T.V., Vorob'eva M.V. Preimushhestva ustanovki s#emnyh protezov s oporoj na implantaty pri polnom otsutstvii zubov na nizhnej cheljusti. Innovacionnoe razvitie. 2017;10(15):81-82.

5. Arushanjan A.R., Konnov V.V., Popko E.S., Pichugina E.N., Razakov D.H., Konnov S.V. Programma dlja opredelenija stepeni myshechno-sustavnoj disfunkcii. Svidetel'stvo o registracii programy dlja JeVM RUS 2016614212 02.03.16.

6. Razakov D.H., Konnov V.V., Arushanjan A.R., Pichugina E.N., Popko E.S. Rol' dinamicheskoj jellektronejrostimuljacii v kompleksnom lechenii myshechno-sustavnoj disfunkcii pacientov s deformacijami zubnyh rjadov i prikusa. Sovremennye problemy nauki i obrazovanija. 2015;6- 0:199.

7. Pichugina E.N., Arushanjan A.R., Konnov V.V., Razakov D.H., Sal'nikov V.N. Sposob ocenki

okkluzionnyh vzaimootnoshenij zubov i zubnyh rjadov. Zhurnal nauchnyh statej: Zdorov'e i obrazovanie v XXI veke. 2016;18:11:52-54.

8. Konnov V.V., Pichugina E.N., Arushanjan A.R., Bizjaev A.A., Mikailova V.A. Jeffektivnost' ortopedicheskikh metodov lechenija pacientov s defektami zubnyh rjadov, oslozhnennymi distal'noj okkluziej v zavisimosti ot topograficheskikh osobennostej visochno-nizhnecheljustnogo sustava. Sovremennaja ortopedicheskaja stomatologija. 2017;28:39-41.

9. Konnov SV, Razakov DKh, Konnov VV, Arushanyan AR, Mukhamedov RN, Khodorich AS, Mikailova VA. Functional status of masticatory muscles at occlusion disturbances accompanied with displaced mandible. Archiv EuroMedica. 2018;8:1:41-42.

10. Konnov SV, Bizyaev AA, Konnov VV, Pichugina EV, Salnikova SN, Khodorich AS, Mikailova VA. Radiological specifics of temporomandibular joint structure in case of dentition issues complicated with distal occlusion. Archiv EuroMedica. 2018;8:1:39-40.